

DIFFERENT PSYCHOLOGICAL METHOD FOR STUDYING ABNORMAL BEHAVIOR PATTERN

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Abstract: Abnormal Psychology is a sub branch of psychology. It is defined as the study of unusual pattern of behavior, emotion and thought. The term 'Abnormal' with its prefix ab (away from) this come to signify the deviance from the Normal, but the concept 'normal' is relative and can vary across the culture and time period. This article shades light on the top four method to study abnormal behavior.

Keywords: Psychology, Abnormal Behavior, Normality, Abnormality, Emotion.

INTRODUCTION:

Abnormal Psychology focuses on the study of the behavior and experience of the abnormal people. It measures for the treatment of abnormal behavior or disorders. The term 'normal' is derived from the word-'Norma', which has its root from 'Norm', therefore meaning a rule or a pattern or standard. The term abnormal with its prefix ab (away from) thus came to the deviance from the normal. According to the statistical criterion average is normal which is explained in bell shaped curve or Gaussian Curve.

THEORY AND DEFINATION:

Abnormal Psychology refer to four D's Criteria -Deviance, Distress, Dysfunction and Denger, use to define abnormal behaviors and mental disorder. Now let's break up the four D's-

Deviance:- This refer behavior of thought, emotion, that differ from normal within a society and culture for a given period.

Distress:- This refer to the negative feeling, emotional pain such as anxiety.

Dysfunction:- It refers to one's inability to perform of every day task and responsibility such as work, school, relationship.

Danger:- It refer to behavior that possess a risk of harm to one self and others.

Different Perspective on Abnormal Psychology: - The following perspective explains behavioral patten in a cultural setting for a given preiod of time.

1) **The Behavioral Perspective:** - It views mental disorder as a maladaptive behavior learned through environmental interaction. It focuses on

observable behavior.

2) **The Cognitive Perspective:** - It focuses on the way that people's thought influence their's emotions. It is assumed that having logical thought patterns would help a person development and maintaining of their's psychological health.

3) **The Medical Perspective:-** It views mental disorder as illness with biological, and similar to physical diseases. It often involves medical intervention to correct chemical imbalance of body.

4) **The Psychodynamics Perspective:-** It explains mental disorder as a result of unconscious feeling, internal conflict generating from childhood Experiences.

Psychological Method for Studying of Abnormal Behavior:- Here We discuss four top method to study abnormal behavior.

1) **Case History Method:-** In case history method one can collect detailed record of an Individual's personal, medical, social, economical, life events. Its a in-depth qualitative Investigations of specific person or group. It aims to understand complex behavior and diagnose condition by collecting extensive data.

2) **Clinical Method:-** It focuses on the Individual in a naturalistic setting providing deep but often subjective insight to their inique problem and situation. It is used by clinical psychologist, psychiatrist, social workers.

3) **Experimental Method:-** In this method one can manipulate one or more Independent variable and observe the effect on dependable Variable under control condition. It is Objective, scientific and Systematic approach.

4) **Follow Up Method:-** It focuses on ongoing assessment to ensure treatment and effectiveness and prevent disorders by measuring symptoms before, during and after therapy.

Conclusion:

Finally, we may say that 'normality' and 'abnormality' are relative concept. Particular one method of above discussed are not deployed in a given situation.

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